

Effect of Heavy Metal Ions on the Hydrolysis of Salicylidene-5-phenyl-1,3,4-thiadiazole Schiff Base

F. A. ADAM* and M. T. EL-HATY

Chemistry Department, Faculty of Science Aswan, Egypt

and

S. A. EL-GYAR

Chemistry Department, Faculty of Science, Assiut, Egypt

Manuscript received 29 December 1986, revised 22 May 1987, accepted 30 October 1987

The hydrolysis of salicylidene-5-phenyl-1,3,4-thiadiazole is investigated kinetically in a series of universal buffer solutions containing 30% (w/w) ethanol at 25°, and the effect of pH on the hydrolysis mechanism is elucidated. The perturbation effect of some heavy metal ions (UO_2^{II} , Th^{IV} and Ce^{III}) on the hydrolysis rate of the title Schiff base has been studied and discussed.

GENERALLY, substituted-1,3,4-thiadiazole Schiff bases have wide application in pharmacological, antileukemic and biological aspects¹⁻⁴. In a previous communication⁵, the kinetic and mechanism of hydrolysis of these compounds was studied in alkaline (NaOH) and acidic (AcOH) media. In continuation of this work, we report here a systematic study concerning the hydrolysis mechanism of salicylidene-5-phenyl-1,3,4-thiadiazole in a series of universal buffer solutions and in the presence of some heavy metal ions, viz. UO_2^{II} , Th^{IV} and Ce^{III} .

Experimental

Salicylidene-5-phenyl-1,3,4-thiadiazole (HL) was prepared by refluxing the equimolar quantities of 5-phenyl-2-amino-1,3,4-thiadiazole and salicylaldehyde in dehydrated ethanol in presence of a small amount of piperidine. The crude solid obtained after cooling the mixture was further recrystallised from ethanol. The product was a yellow colour solid, m.p. 173° (Found: C, 64.00; H, 3.65; N, 14.55. $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{10}\text{N}_3\text{OS}$ calcd. for: C, 64.04; H, 3.93; N, 14.84%); λ_{max} (EtOH) 209 ($\epsilon=25\,000\text{ cm}^2\text{ mol}^{-1}$), 256 (15 000), 315 (17 300), 373 (9 300) and 465 (300); ν_{max} 1610 (C=N imine), 1630b (C=N(b) within ring), 740b (C=S) and 680 cm^{-1} . These results agree with the structure of salicylidene-5-phenyl-1,3,4-thiadiazole (HL).

The ir spectra (KBr) was recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 599A spectrophotometer. Uv and visible spectra were measured with a Shimadzu 240 digital spectrophotometer using 1 cm matched silica cells. Universal buffer solutions (pH=2.0 to 11.6) were prepared according to the method described by Britton⁶. pH data for the kinetic runs were

obtained with a M.V. 87 digital practionic pH meter (± 0.005 unit).

To account for the difference in acidity, basicity, dielectric constant and ion activities in aqueous 30% (w/w) ethanol solutions relative to pure aqueous ones, the measured pH values of the former solutions were recorded as described by Qouhert⁷,

$$\text{pH}^* = \text{pH}(\text{R}) - \delta$$

where, pH^* is the corrected reading and $\text{pH}(\text{R})$ is the meter reading obtained in a partially aqueous medium, where the pH meter is standardised using aqueous buffer. The value⁷ of δ of the aqueous buffer solution containing 30% (w/w) ethanol is 0.08.

Stock solutions (1×10^{-2} mol dm^{-3}) of Schiff base, $\text{UO}_2(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{Th}(\text{NO}_3)_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $\text{Ce}(\text{NO}_3)_3 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ were prepared by dissolving the requisite amount of each in pure ethanol.

Kinetic measurements: The hydrolysis rate of the Schiff base (HL) was studied spectrophotometrically in a series of universal buffer solutions at pH range 2.0–11.6 containing 30% (w/w) ethanol. The effect of UO_2^{II} , Th^{IV} and Ce^{III} ions on the hydrolysis rate was investigated as follows. The reaction mixtures to be studied were prepared with the Schiff base solution, the aqueous universal buffer solutions and stock of metal solution in a glass stoppered tube. These tubes were placed in an ultrathermostat ($\pm 0.05^\circ$). After temperature equilibrium was attained, a known volume of the reactants was mixed rapidly in a 25 ml measuring flask. The mixing time was taken as the zero time. The rate at which the Schiff base hydrolysed was follow by measuring the absorbance at $\lambda_{\text{max}}=375$ nm at intervals. The amounts of the Schiff base were calculated by applying Beer's law ($c=9\,300$

$\text{cm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1}$). The rate constants were calculated from the first order reaction, where the reactions were followed kinetically up to about 50% completion.

Results and Discussion

Hydrolysis in absence of metal ions: The hydrolysis of $1 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ of salicylidene-5-phenyl-1,3,4-thiadiazole was studied in a series of universal buffer solutions containing 30% (w/w) ethanol of pH varying from 2.0 to 11.6 with a constant ionic strength of 0.04 mol dm^{-3} at 25° . The observed first order rate constants for hydrolysis are determined and plotted against pH values (Fig. 1). Fig. 1 exhibits a minimum hydrolysis rate in the neutral zone of pH 6–8, and it increases as the pH of the medium is lowered to pH 2.0. In the

Fig. 1. Variation of the first order rate constant (s^{-1}) with pH for the hydrolysis of (HL) at 25° .

alkaline region the hydrolysis rate increases as the pH is increased and it reaches a plateau in the media of $\text{pH} \geq 10.0$. This behaviour can be interpreted as follows. (i) In acidic medium, at $\text{pH} < 6$ it is well known that the rate-limiting step of the hydrolysis reaction is the addition of water to the protonated Schiff base⁸⁻¹². Thus, it is expected that the hydrolysis rate of (HL) increases as pH of the medium is lowered, due to the increase in the protonated Schiff base concentration in the same direction. A mono six-membered ring is formed from the coordination of both hydrogen and oxygen water atoms with inner nitrogen atom of the thiadiazole ring and aldamine carbon atom, respectively. Thus, in a slow step the carbinolamine

intermediate is formed and it is suggested to be the rate-limiting step. The second step in the hydrolysis mechanism is decomposition of the carbinolamine with fast rate to amine and aldehyde,

(ii) In the pH range 6–8, where a lower rate of hydrolysis is measured, the rate-limiting step of the hydrolysis mechanism is suggested to be the addition of water to the neutral Schiff base. In this pH range the Schiff base is capable of forming two six-membered rings as a result of the interaction of the added water molecule with the Schiff base as well as the intermolecular hydrogen bond liable to exist between imine nitrogen atom and the *ortho*-hydroxy group. Accordingly, the slow hydrolysis rate observed in this pH range can presumably be ascribed to the expected high stability of carbinolamine intermediate in chelated intermolecular H-bond. The following scheme represents the hydrolysis mechanism in neutral media,

(iii) At $\text{pH} > 8$, the hydrolysis rate increases with the ascent in basic medium, and at $\text{pH} \geq 10$ the hydrolysis rate reaches a plateau (Fig. 1). This behaviour can be explained by the principle that in basic medium the hydroxylic Schiff base exists in phenoxide form and hydrolysed as anion imine (L^-)¹². The ionisation constant¹¹ $\text{p}K_{\text{OH}} = 7.35$, thus the more or less constant hydrolysis rate observed in the media of $\text{pH} \geq 10$ can be ascribed to the extreme slowness of OH^- attack on the imine carbon atom under the effect of the high electron donor character of the ionised *ortho*-hydroxy group. Furthermore, the expected high charge conjugation between the phenoxide and thiadiazole moieties will result in a high stability of the carbinolamine intermediate in such cases.

Hydrolysis in presence of metal ions: The hydrolysis of $1 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ of salicylidene-5-

phenyl-1,3,4-thiadiazole has been investigated in neutral medium of aqueous 30% (w/w) ethanol (pH=7) in the presence of some metal ions, having different concentrations of each UO_2^{II} , Th^{IV} and Ce^{III} ions ($1 \times 10^{-5} - 3 \times 10^{-4}$ mol dm^{-3}) at 25° . These metal ions were chosen due to their interesting character in forming complexes with a high coordination number. The first order hydrolysis rate constant at each metal ion concentration was calculated and the results obtained are listed in Table 1. Examination of Table 1 reveals that the presence of metal ion greatly accelerates the rate of hydrolysis of (HL), where a more or less constant rate is achieved at M^{n+} : Schiff ratio equal to 1 : 1.

TABLE 1—FIRST ORDER RATE CONSTANT VALUES FOR HYDROLYSIS OF 1×10^{-4} mol dm^{-3} (HL) IN 30% (w/w) ETHANOL—NEUTRAL MEDIUM OF BUFFER SOLUTION MIXTURE IN PRESENCE OF METAL ION AT 25°

[M] ⁿ⁺ × 10 ⁻⁴	First order rate constant (× 10 ³ s ⁻¹)		
	Th ^{IV}	UO ₂ ^{II}	Ce ^{III}
0.0		Rate constant (K) = 1.72×10^{-3} s ⁻¹	
0.2	6.47	7.86	8.95
0.4	7.95	8.55	9.70
0.6	9.00	9.98	11.05
0.8	10.80	11.55	13.64
1.0	12.55	13.33	15.08
2.0	12.50	13.30	15.05
3.0	12.55	13.30	15.00

Moreover, with respect to the effect of nature of metal ion on the hydrolysis rate, one can observe the behaviour that the rate increases along the sequence $\text{Th}^{IV} \rightarrow \text{UO}_2^{II} \rightarrow \text{Ce}^{III}$. An attempt to explain these observations is given below.

Since the Schiff base under investigation has a high tendency to coordinate to metal ion as a bidentate ligand, through the imine nitrogen and phenolic oxygen atoms¹⁴, one might expect that in the presence of a metal ion the substrate exists mainly in a metal complex form. Accordingly, the azomethine carbon atom is expected to carry a high positive charge relative to that in absence of metal ion. This results in a higher nucleophilic attack by water on this carbon atom. Furthermore, the decomposition of the carbinolamine intermediate in a metal complex form is expected to occur faster than that in the free form. This is due to the significant stabilising extended charge conjugation (between the salicylidimine moiety and the thiadiazole ring). This effect is not available in case of the metal complexes of carbinolamine due to the formation of six-membered chelated ring resulting in isolation of the thiadiazole ring from

the rest of the molecule. Moreover, the high tendency of the hydrolysis product salicylaldehyde to coordinate to metal ion will result in high Schiff hydrolysis rate in presence of metal ion. The hydrolysis mechanism in the presence of metal ion can be represented as

The structure, the stability constant k_f ($\text{dm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1}$) and the free energy of formation $-\Delta G$ (kcal mol^{-1}) of 1 : 1 salicylidene-5-phenyl-1,3,4-thiadiazole complexes with UO_2^{II} , Th^{IV} and Ce^{III} ions were studied in our previous work¹⁴. The results show that the stability of these complexes follows the order, $\text{Th}^{IV} > \text{UO}_2^{II} > \text{Ce}^{III}$. Thus, the observed increase in hydrolysis rate as the metal ion is changed along the sequence, $\text{Th}^{IV} \rightarrow \text{UO}_2^{II} \rightarrow \text{Ce}^{III}$ is consistent with the observed decrease in stability of the Schiff base metal complex in the same direction, i.e. high hydrolysis rate.

References

1. R. A. MORTON and G. A. PITT, *Biochem. J.*, 1955, **59**, 128.
2. M. M. CIOTTI, S. R. HUMPHREIS, J. M. VENDITTI, N. O. KAPLAN and A. GOLDIN, *Cancer Res.*, 1960, **20**, 1195.
3. G. MAFFEI, E. TESTA and E. ETTORE, *J. Farmaco.*, 1958, **13**, 187.
4. B. WITKOP and L. K. RAMACHANDRAM, *Metabolism J.*, 1964, **13**, 1016.
5. F. A. ADAM, EL-HATY and A. A. GABR, *J. Chin. Chem. Soc.*, 1986, in the press.
6. H. T. S. BRITTON, "Hydrogen Ions", Chapman and Hall, London, 1952, p. 364.
7. G. QUERRER, *Bull. Soc. Chim. Fr.*, 1967, 1412.
8. R. L. REEVS, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1965, **30**, 8129.
9. P. HAAKE and J. W. WASTON, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1970, **35**, 4063.
10. S. PATAI, "The Chemistry of the Carbon Nitrogen Double Bond", Wiley, New York, 1970, p. 468.
11. J. J. CHARRETT and E. HOFFMAN, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1979, **44**, 2256.
12. A. C. DASH, B. DASH and P. K. MAHAPATRA, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1983, 1503.
13. M. E. MAHMOUD, R. ABDEL-HAMIDE and F. ABDEL-GOAD, *Z. Phys. Chem. (Leipzig)*, 1981, 262.
14. M. T. EL-HATY and F. A. ADAM, *Bull. Soc. Chim. Fr.*, 1986, **5**, 729.